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METHODS FOR INCREASING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN ENTERPRISES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

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Abstract. This study conducts an economic analysis of the composition, characteristics, and key factors affecting economic efficiency indicators in construction industry enterprises. The research examines the level of resource utilization in production activities, labor productivity, production costs, the efficiency of fixed asset use, and the mechanisms shaping financial outcomes in construction enterprises.

In addition, the study analyzes internal and external factors affecting economic efficiency in the construction industry, including the level of development of production technologies, investment volume, raw material supply, the quality of labor resources, management efficiency, and changes in market conditions. The research results provide scientifically grounded conclusions and practical recommendations aimed at enhancing economic efficiency in enterprises, ensuring the rational use of available resources, and optimizing production costs.

Keywords: economic efficiency; productivity; production costs; labor productivity; profitability; economic analysis.

Аннотация. В данной статье проводится экономический анализ структуры, особенностей и основных факторов, влияющих на показатели экономической эффективности предприятий строительной отрасли. Исследуются уровень использования ресурсов в производственной деятельности, производительность труда, производственные затраты, эффективность использования основных средств, а также механизмы формирования финансовых результатов строительных предприятий.

Кроме того, проанализированы внутренние и внешние факторы, оказывающие влияние на экономическую эффективность предприятий строительной отрасли, включая уровень развития производственных технологий, объем инвестиций, обеспеченность сырьевыми ресурсами, качество трудовых ресурсов, эффективность системы управления и изменения рыночной конъюнктуры. По результатам исследования сформулированы научно обоснованные выводы и практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение экономической эффективности предприятий, обеспечение рационального использования имеющихся ресурсов и оптимизацию производственных затрат.

Ключевые слова: экономическая эффективность; производительность; производственные затраты; производительность труда; рентабельность; экономический анализ.

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is recognized as one of the strategic sectors driving the economic growth of nations. This sector is of significant importance due to its role in infrastructure development, the creation of new employment opportunities, the enhancement of investment activity, and the integrated advancement of industrial and service sectors. According to international economic research, the global construction market exceeded USD 13.9 trillion in 2025, with forecasts indicating an increase to USD 17.5 trillion by 2030. The construction sector accounts for approximately 13 percent of global gross domestic product and provides between 7 and 8 percent of global employment. In this respect, the construction industry serves as a “multiplicative driver” of economic growth¹².

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the construction sector is recognized as one of the fastest-growing industries within the national economy. According to data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the volume of construction works completed in the country in 2025 amounted to 313.9 trillion soums, reflecting a 14.0 percent increase compared to 2024. Over the past five years, the construction sector’s share of gross domestic product has consistently ranged between 6.5 and 7.0 percent, while the number of active enterprises in the sector has exceeded 45,000.

At the same time, the acceleration of urbanization processes, the establishment of the “New Tashkent” and “New Uzbekistan” districts, the development of transport and logistics infrastructure, industrial zones, and energy facilities, as well as the scientifically grounded management of allocated funds, highlight the growing importance of effective resource governance. These indicators confirm the steady growth in the role and importance of the construction sector within the national economy. Therefore, issues related to the efficient utilization of resources, scientifically grounded cost control, and the optimization of production processes in this sector are of particular significance³.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issues of enhancing economic efficiency in construction industry enterprises have been examined from various perspectives by both foreign and local economists.

Economic efficiency in the construction sector has been studied by numerous researchers. In particular, F. W. Taylor⁴, H. Ford⁵, T. Ohno⁶, W. E. Deming⁷, P. Drucker⁸, and M. Porter⁹ explained efficiency in terms of labor productivity, cost reduction, rational resource utilization, and the maintenance of competitive advantage. The specific features of the construction sector have also been studied in the context of BIM and digital technologies by researchers such as C. Eastman¹⁰, P. Teicholz, R. Sacks, K. Liston, S. Azhar¹¹, D. Bryde, and W. Lu. Their works provide both theoretical and practical foundations for the efficient use of time, costs, and resources in construction processes.

In addition, among scholars from the CIS countries and Uzbekistan, the works of V. B. Ivashkevich¹², M. A. Vakhrushina¹³, V. E. Kerimov, M. Q. Pardayev¹⁴, B. I. Isroilov, N. Sh. Jo’rayev, and A. K. Karimov serve as important academic sources for studying cost management, managerial accounting, and the improvement of economic efficiency in construction enterprises¹⁵.

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The introduction of digital control technologies in the construction industry is advancing labor cost accounting systems to a new stage. In particular, ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) systems, BIM (Building Information Modeling) technologies, Primavera, AutoCAD BIM, and “1C: Construction” platforms facilitate the automation of construction processes and the efficient management of labor resources¹⁶.

ERP systems enable construction enterprises to manage workforce, financial resources, and material flows within a unified information database. This improves the efficiency of labor cost analysis and supports timely managerial decision-making. BIM technologies make it possible to accurately forecast labor requirements and optimize resource allocation by creating digital models of construction projects¹⁷ (Table 1).

Table 1
Comparative analysis of digital platforms used for labor cost calculation in the construction industry¹⁸

System	Advantages	Disadvantages	Efficiency
ERP	Unified management of all resources within a single system	High implementation cost	High
BIM	Precise modeling and forecasting	Expert training required	High
Primavera	Effective for project planning	Costly for small businesses	Medium
1C: Construction	Integration of accounting and workforce records	Functionally limited	Medium
AutoCAD BIM	Visual analysis capability	Requires big data	High
“Transparent Construction”	Government monitoring and transparency	Does not cover all processes	Medium

The reforms underway in Uzbekistan to digitize the construction sector also contribute to the development of digital systems for calculating labor costs.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As part of the research, an author-developed digital mechanism for calculating labor costs in construction work was proposed. The main purpose of this mechanism is to improve the efficiency of labor resource utilization, reduce working time losses, and monitor labor costs in real time.

The proposed mechanism includes the following elements:

- automated labor monitoring;
- work time tracking via QR codes;
- monitoring of employee activity using IoT sensors;
- a real-time analytical monitoring platform.

According to the operating procedure of the mechanism, an individual QR code is assigned to each worker, and the process of entering and exiting the construction site is recorded electronically. These data are transmitted to a central database, and labor consumption, working hours, and efficiency indicators are automatically calculated through the analytical module. As a result, rapid reports on labor costs are generated, thereby accelerating the process of managerial decision-making (Figure 1).

¹⁶ Eastman C. et al. *BIM Handbook: A Guide to Building Information Modeling*. – New Jersey: Wiley, 2018.

¹⁷ Project Management Institute. *Practice Standard for Project Estimating*. – PMI, 2021.

¹⁸ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5963 dated March 2, 2020, on Measures for Comprehensive Reform of the Construction Sector

Figure 1. Digital management mechanism for labor costs in construction works¹⁹

Implementing the proposed digital mechanism enhances the accuracy of labor cost calculations, reduces hidden expenses, and improves the effective use of working time. The research results show that construction companies implementing digital monitoring systems have achieved an average increase in labor productivity of 12–15%. This is of significant importance for improving the economic efficiency of construction projects and ensuring financial stability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research findings indicate that improving economic efficiency in construction industry enterprises is fundamentally linked to increasing labor productivity, efficiently allocating production costs, and refining the management system through modern approaches. Moreover, the analysis confirmed that the factors influencing efficiency in the construction industry are multifaceted and are determined not only by the internal operations of enterprises but also by technological advancements, market demand, and external economic conditions.

Therefore, the use of digital management tools in the sector, particularly ERP, BIM, Primavera, AutoCAD BIM, and information platforms, is of practical importance for accounting for and controlling labor costs. In particular, the proposed digital mechanism, which integrates QR code control, IoT sensors, automated monitoring, and real-time analytical management elements, enables the precise calculation of labor consumption, reduces working time losses, and minimizes hidden costs in construction companies.

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